

FUNDAMENTALS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS ON MOTHER LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY LESSONS IN PRIMARY CLASS

Haydarova Kamola Ergashboy kizi

Trainee-researcher of Gulistan State University

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Abstract. *Since elementary school students are at the first stage of education, teaching critical thinking brings some difficulties. This article discusses the issues of improving students' critical thinking skills in mother tongue and reading literacy classes.*

Keywords: *critical thinking, method, student, reading, language.*

INTRODUCTION

In the theory of world language education, it is recognized that pragmatic competence arises as a set of educational and linguistic competences such as working with information, being aware of and using science and technology innovations, national and general cultural, spelling, sign, methodological literacy, speech activity and maturity. This is the basis for the scientific-methodical improvement of educational technologies aimed at the formation and development of students' listening, reading, speaking, writing, understanding, comprehension, application, evaluation based on the phonetic, lexical, morphological, syntactic, methodological and semantic analysis of linguistic and speech pragmatic artistic texts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the education sector of every country, the development of speech in children is recognized as the main structural element of the system. In Uzbekistan, the development of children's speech during the initial stages of continuous education - preschool and primary education - is defined as an important direction of the pedagogical process. The formation of the global information and innovative educational environment, the increase in the social need for the development of human capital, requires the young generation to mature in all aspects, develop intellectually, and use speech opportunities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the course of the research, the principles that are prioritized in the process of speech development by working on the text in primary reading classes were also identified.

1. The principle of taking age characteristics into account. This principle means that it is appropriate to organize the process of working on the text, form educational tasks, and give individual tasks to students based on their age characteristics. Taking into account the age characteristics of students: prevents them from being mentally and physically exhausted; ensures an efficient process of working with the text; saves time; allows to achieve the learning goal.

2. Principle of practical approach. This principle represents the process of working with the text in primary school reading classes, the basis of educational tasks on practical exercises, game methods. Students perform the exercises on the basis of systematic, consistently organized practical activities related to reading and writing (expressive reading, telling the content of the text, making a plan, working with the dictionary, independent work on the text) [6].

3. The principle of emotional-aesthetic approach. This principle describes the fact that the texts included in the "Reading Book" textbook intended for elementary grades serve to arouse emotional experiences in students, to give them aesthetic pleasure. The awakening of emotional experiences in students, the occurrence of aesthetic pleasure, educates their feelings, positive attitude towards existence, and aesthetic taste.

4. The principle of systematicity and continuity. This principle refers to the systematic and continuous process of learning activities, which consists of working on the text in primary school reading classes. In primary school reading lessons, initially small texts are used, which are familiar to students in their daily activities, and gradually, on the basis of gradual (evolutionary) development, texts are used that allow them to introduce new knowledge and enrich speech with new words.

5. The principle of artistry and expressiveness. The texts studied in working with texts in elementary reading classes have artistic value and develop students' interest and motivation in books and reading. The task of the teacher in the course of the lesson is to ensure the expressive teaching of the text, which leads to the acquisition of the skills of the students to put the emphasis correctly, to observe half and full stops, to pay attention to the pace and tone of speech.

6. The principle of interactivity and awareness. By its essence, the principle of interactivity, as in modern lessons, means that the educational activities aimed at working with the text in the elementary reading classes are organized in small groups, and the individual activity of the student takes place within the activity of small groups. According to it, educational tasks are performed in small groups, on the basis of mutual, joint actions of students. It is necessary for the teacher to be able to ensure that each student is active in the performance of joint educational tasks. Ensuring that each student independently expresses at least one idea about the studied text creates the ground for the development of free, creative, critical thinking skills in them.

The principle of awareness represents a creative approach to the text by each student, a sufficient and correct understanding of its content, an approach to the given assignment, questions based on thinking and reflection. The students' conscious attitude towards reading the text and understanding its content is clearly reflected in the emergence of various questions about the reality expressed in the text during the learning process. "Why?", "Why so?", "What if.. what would have happened?", "Why did it happen?" Asking dozens of questions like this shows that they are deeply learning the content of the text [7].

7. The principle of indicativeness. From a psychological point of view, elementary school students perceive knowledge figuratively. And the use of instructional tools in the course of the lesson ensures that their ideas are clear. Therefore, the use of instructional tools in working with the text in elementary reading classes helps to enrich students' imagination and expand their worldview.

In primary grades, as a guide, natural objects (nature scenery, constructions, objects, equipment, etc.), various creatures (plants, birds, animals), behavior of individuals are used from the pictures given in the "Alphabet", "Reading Book", "Mother Tongue" textbooks. actions (exemplary behavior, manners, behavior, life experience) can be used.

8. The principle of multivariability. The use of educational and test tasks in determining the level of development of students' speech by working with the text in elementary reading classes gives effective results. The multi-variant nature of educational and test assignments helps students to develop logical thinking and analytical skills.

9. The principle of interdisciplinarity. When working with text in elementary grades, there is an interaction between the lessons "Reading" and "Mother language". After all, if students are introduced to the rules of expression of oral and written speech in the "Mother Language" class, in the "Reading" classes, practical actions related to expressive reading of the text, its written or oral presentation, working on the dictionary, and independent work on the text are organized in accordance with these rules.

If the story and the conversation are skillfully combined, it becomes easier to implement the goals and tasks of the lesson. Observations have shown that there are also specific problems of preparing students for reading. Some teachers exaggerate the size of the introductory interview, spend 10-15 minutes on preparatory work, and throw questions out of order. In reading lessons, a large part of the lesson is spent in speech, considering other activities that are not directly related to reading the text. Therefore, 30-35 minutes should be allocated for reading.

Appropriateness and expediency of the conversation and story, the amount of questions, their content and logic, and the size of the story should be the focus of the teacher's attention. Usually, when reading topics that are close to the students' life experiences, there is often no need for dialogue. However, an introduction by the teacher to guide the students to the topic is definitely necessary. Without it, it is difficult for students to fully understand the work [8].

Before reading the stories on the historical topic, the teacher determines the knowledge of the students about the history of the Motherland and the great figures of its glorious past.

Preparatory work before reading poetic texts is more complicated. The task of holistic perception of lyrical works is to create a harmonious mood in the psyche of the poet, to motivate the students to feel joy, wonder, and sadness together with the poet. In this case, the introduction of the teacher should be short, goal-oriented and help to enter the poet's world.

Reading the text and analyzing it. In the process of reading the text, students get acquainted with its ideological and artistic features, events reflected in the work. Based on the genre characteristics of the work, the text can be taught expressively, interpreted and divided into roles. Reading the literary text helps to clearly imagine the scenes described by the author, to draw appropriate conclusions from the actions of the heroes of the work.

CONCLUSION

If the intended result of speech development is not achieved in the first year of education in general secondary schools, the process of speech development by working on the text in the 2nd grade reading lessons will be difficult. This, in turn, has a negative impact on the learning of all educational subjects by the student. That is why it is necessary for the teacher to organize each lesson based on a strict plan.

In methodology science, the re-description of the text in two different ways is noted. These are: a) describing with words; b) graphic representation.

Description with words is a complex type of work, which involves accurately recreating the event, character or scene described in the work with the help of words. Such description requires the correct choice and pronunciation of words as one of the important means of developing students' speech.

Reimagining the text is of great importance in working on the text and develops students' creative abilities. The correct use of recapitulation creates favorable conditions for readers to clearly imagine the life scenes described by the writer in the work.

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